

Pest Control and Management

WEEDS

Schoenoplectus corymbosus (Roth ex Roem. and Schult.) J. Raynal, a new weed in ricefields in India

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Large numbers of *Schoenoplectus corymbosus* (80.8/m²) in standing water of ricefields around Mudigere, Karnataka, India, affect crop growth and productivity.

The stout rhizomatous perennial grows to 70-110 cm ht (see figure). Stems are tubular and bear inflorescences about 15 cm from the tip. The inflorescence has 4-8 rays bearing clustered, often proliferous spikelets. Bracts are about 3 cm long, erect and rigid. Spikelets are ellipsoid, about 8 × 4 mm. Glumes are oblong, acute, with a narrow, minutely excurrent midrib. It has no bristles. The nut is obovoid, about 2 mm long, unequally triquetrous, black and shiny. Average dry weight of a single clump

Schoenoplectus corymbosus, a new weed in ricefields in the hill region of Karnataka, India.

is 9.72 g and there are around 39.2 stems in each clump.

In a rice plot with large numbers of *S. corymbosus*, yield was 30.7% less

than in a *S. corymbosus*-free plot.

This weed of rice is new for the hill region of Karnataka. □

Integrated weed management in transplanted rice

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The effect of manual (hand weeding), chemical (preemergence or postemergence herbicides), and cultural (azolla dual cropping) methods of weed control alone or in combination was studied in transplanted IR50 during 1985 kharif. The treatments were in a randomized block design replicated 3 times.

Weed flora at the experimental site

Effect of weed control treatments on transplanted rice. Madurai, India.

Treatment ^a	Weed dry weight at harvest (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
Butachlor 1.25 kg ai/ha + HW 25 DT	12.94	6.4	687.4
Thiobencarb 1.50 kg ai/ha + HW 25 DT	14.20	6.3	659.4
Oxadiazon 0.75 kg ai/ha + HW 25 DT	15.06	6.2	641.5
2,4-D sodium salt 1.0 kg ai/ha + HW 40 DT	15.80	6.2	658.4
Azolla 1 t/ha 10 DT	34.20	5.1	508.0
Azolla 1 t/ha + HW 25 DT	17.20	5.6	565.5
Azolla 1 t/ha + HW 40 DT	16.60	5.7	586.8
Butachlor 1.25 kg ai/ha + azolla 1 t/ha	17.66	5.8	606.2
Thiobencarb 1.5 kg ai/ha + azolla 1 t/ha	17.34	5.8	594.2
Oxadiazon 0.75 kg ai/ha + azolla 1 t/ha	17.86	5.7	581.6
HW 25 and 40 DT	13.20	6.3	664.2
Unweeded check	45.20	5.0	496.0
CD 5%	2.32	0.3	—

^a DT = days after transplanting, HW = hand weeding.